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THE ORGANIC CARBON (OC) AND ELEMENTAL CARBON (EC) IN 5 EUROPEAN CITIES.

THE ICARUS EXPERIENCE

R. Franco Peteira¹, P. Morillo¹, A. Aguiar¹, MC. Torres¹, S. García Dos Santos-Alves¹, T. Maggos², T. Kanduč³, D. Kocman³, C. Degrendele⁴, S. Karakitsios⁵

¹ National Center for Environmental Health (ISCIII) (Madrid). ² University Demokritos (Athens), ³ Jožef Stefan Institute, ⁴ Research Centre for Toxic Compounds in the Environment, ⁵ Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

rfranco@isciii.es

The aim of H2020 ICARUS project is to develop tools for European cities to reduce the levels of atmospheric pollutants and their effects. These tools will require changes of both policy makers and citizens. This is made using network data and estimated health impacts. Also, important pollutant data as OC+EC which levels are not available, were measured. The measured PM_{2,5}, OC and EC levels, in Athens, Brno, Ljubljana, Madrid and Thessaloniki are in 3 typical air quality stations (traffic, urban and city background) during winter and summer 2017. In summer the results showed that OC and EC levels are very similar in the 5 cities among each station type. A similar trend has been described by the bibliography^[1], elsewhere. In Madrid the mean OC levels varied from 3,82 µgC/m³ (traffic) to 3,65 µgC/m³ and 2,86 µgC/m³ (urban and city background). In Brno OC values were 3,55 µgC/m³, 3,43 µgC/m³ and 2,13 µgC/m³. Also, the OC/EC ratio showed lower values in all traffic stations because of an increase of EC levels (1,77 µgC/m³ at Madrid and 1,68 µgC/m³ at Brno) in comparison with the 0,51 µgC/m³ and from 0,18 µgC/m³ for city background for the same locations.

Winter is different and OC values in Brno are higher than Madrid, while EC values are similar. In Madrid OC levels varied from 4,43 µgC/m³ (traffic) to 3,76 µgC/m³ and 3,10 µgC/m³ (urban and city background). In Brno OC values were 8,54 µgC/m³, 10,57 µgC/m³ and 4,08 µgC/m³ instead. So, an increase of OC/EC ratios in Brno took place. Athens is similar to Brno and it has been described. EC concentrations increased during winter. In Madrid (Brno) showed for traffic 1,93 µgC/m³ (2,31 µgC/m³), urban 1,55 µgC/m³ (1,27 µgC/m³) and city background 0,77 µgC/m³ (0,58 µgC/m³). Those differences are due to different OC and EC sources during winter time where domestic heating or secondary particles formation are predominant.

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References:

[1] Variability of carbonaceous aerosols in remote, rural, urban and industrial environments in Spain : implications for air quality policy. X. Querol Atmos.Chem.Phys